

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF UZBEK FOLKLORE**Dilovor Avlakulov**

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ANNOTATION

The term folklore in the article and his to himself special features illuminated. In particular, Uzbek folklore, his types scientific in terms of described.

Key words: Folklore, fairy tale proverb, matal, riddle, askiya, song, dirge.

INTRODUCTION

Folklore works his own vitality, social nature, ideological essence and to himself special artistic features with separate stands People 's work, customs, life condition, desire, struggle and victories his t e mas and ideological reflection in the content is enough.

Folklore of his works nationalism feature their vitality and which one worldview protection to do with will be connected. This feature is mainly folklore in his works there is of the main idea it comes out of the essence. Folklore works to himself special artistic also has a template . Especially a fairy tale and in epics there is plot and composition story to do style characterful each two to the genre special plot events always to himself special start and to completion have will be Such feature written in literature does not occur.

English in 1846 archaeologist W. J. Thoms take entered In the 1880s and 1890s, the term " Folklore "was used a lot used in countries, including Russia started in Uzbekistan initially, "oral literature", "mouth literature" terms used. The term "folklore " dates back to the mid -1930s used started Hadi Zarif in 1939. "**Uzbek folklore** " chrestomathy publication after , this the term Uzbek in folklore studies strong place took.

People creativity - people of the masses artistic, creative-practical and amateur activity, traditional material and intangible of culture people oral artistic creativity (*folklore*), folk music (*music folklore*) people theater (*view art*), folk games (*dance*), puppetry , people descriptive and practical decoration art and technical and artistic amateur such as was , live execution conditions and diary in practice until us arrived came.

Folklore is the people creativity the science of Folklore different in periods and different countries ethnography, literature, musicology, anthropology and of sociology one part as looking at came Later on people art (*folk oral creativity, music folklore, dance, theater, circus as*) a learner independent and as a special subject develops.

Music folklore .

Uzbek music in art of the epic two performance style present: Khorezm epic performance and Surkhandarya - Kashkadarya performance styles. Khorezm epic executive of the epic known part word with expressed and known one pieces a song in the form of to the tune put it is said. Performance in the process storytellers tor, harmon, dutor, doyra, bulamon from the instruments they use The same at the time, Bolabakhshi nickname with famous was Kurbannazar Abdullayev creativity and execution style wide popularized.

Surkhan oasis epic performance ancient to style based on is round accompanied by execution will be done. This oasis main musical genres calculated epics the same at the time one series execution to the roads have Har one direction to himself special execution traditions formed and that's it worthy has successors. Our people famous from epic writers follow Jumanbulbul son, Po`Ikan poet, Islam poet, Abdulla Nuraliyev and others blessed creativity they did

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aritual, to a person health wish, his in marriage daily life in his life good luck to bring or a person of life important points note achieve, celebrate in order to special held, people between strictly pineapple come in stay away to behavior it is said.

Ritual as *FOLKLORE* transfer during execution to be done a song and sayings readable a spell and to prayers it is said.

Transfer time , place and style , functions and participants composition with ceremony folklore two to the part is divided . **These are :**

1. Seasonal ceremonies folklore .
2. Family-household ceremonies folklore .

Family-household ceremonies are colorful is conditional _ respectively three to the group divided into :

1. Wedding ceremonies .
2. Mourning ceremonies .
3. Speak magic to the power based on ceremonies .

Wedding Rituals: "Cradle". "wedding", "Khatna wedding", "Marriage weddings".

Mourning Rituals: "Weeping", "Mourning". side by side".

The word magic to the power based on ceremonies: "People spells", "Spiritual in diseases readable spells", "Badik " and "Kinna". enters

Summary as that's it separately to emphasize of the nation marriage style, national values and traditions people oral in his work own on the contrary finds People oral creativity of the people who that shows mirror is the world.

Besides, the people oral of his creation own creative metody there is become him conditional respectively romanticism type creative method because it is possible folklore in his works fiction, artistic fictions, life basis to be, kneaded imaginary food and events life describe to himself special style as manifestation will be

People oral poetic of his creation main feature creative process-creativity and performance of the process collective activity charact has His orality, variation, mass, traditionality, anonymity others like collective activity by created elements of poetics, traditional style tools based on occurs. It is specific listeners to the group intended to be and coll active by confession only when done social and historical importance occupation is enough.

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